

Substituent effects on the spontaneous cleavage of α -methylbenzyl-*gem*-dichlorides in aqueous solution

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The solvolysis reactions of α -methylbenzyl-*gem*-dichlorides in water proceed by a stepwise mechanism through α -chloro- α -methylbenzyl carbocation intermediates, which are captured by water with a rate constant k_s to give the corresponding acetophenones as the sole detectable products.

The substitution reactions of benzyl derivatives have been studied for most of this century¹, and these investigations have been several to the development of the theory of nucleophilic substitution at saturated carbon^{1,2}. In the study of solvolysis reactions of some benzylchlorides, benzalchlorides and polychloromethyl ethers it was concluded that these reactions proceed through stable carbocation intermediates. This was attributed to the contributions of additional structures in which positive charge was placed on α -chlorine³.

Results and discussion

The solvolysis reactions of α -methylbenzyl-*gem*-dichlorides in water at 25°C and $I = 1.0 M$ (NaClO₄) gave the corresponding acetophenones as the sole detectable product (99%). First-order solvolysis rate constants for these reactions in the absence of chloride ion, k_{solv} (s⁻¹) were determined by monitoring the appearance of corresponding acetophenone by UV spectroscopy. The normalized rate constant ratio, $k_{\text{obsd}}/k_{\text{solv}}$, for α -methylbenzyl-*gem*-dichloride, where k_{obsd} is the observed rate constant at a given concentration of chloride ion and k_{solv} is the rate constant in the absence of added chloride ion decreased with increasing [Cl⁻]. The chloride ion inhibition shows that the reactions

of α -methylbenzyl-*gem*-dichlorides proceed by stepwise mechanism through the diffusionally equilibrated α -chloro- α -methylbenzyl carbocation (Cl-1⁺) that can be trapped competitively by added chloride ion and solvent water (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

This kind of common ion inhibition on the solvolysis rates was observed for all the starting compounds studied. The linear plot ($r = 0.9997$) of the data according to eq. (1) derived for the mechanism shown in Scheme 1 gives the values of k_{Cl}/k_s and are given in Table 1.

$$\frac{k_{\text{solv}}}{k_{\text{obsd}}} = 1 + \left(\frac{k_{\text{Cl}}}{k_s} \right) [\text{Cl}^-] \quad (1)$$

The common ion inhibition of the solvolysis of the α -methylbenzyl-*gem*-dichlorides by added chloride ion provides classic evidence for a stepwise D_N + A_N (S_N1)⁴ mechanism, with rate determining cleavage of α -

Table 1. Solvolysis of α -methylbenzyl-*gem*-dichlorides in aqueous solution at 25°C and $I = 1.00 M$ (NaClO₄)

Y	$k_{\text{solv}}/\text{s}^{-1}$	k_{Cl}/k_s (M ⁻¹)	k_s/s^{-1}	σ_p	$\Delta H_{\text{solv}}^{\#}$ kJ/mol	$\Delta S_{\text{solv}}^{\#}$ jK/mol	$\Delta H_s^{\#}$ kJ/mol	$\Delta S_s^{\#}$ jK/mol
4-CH ₃ O	25.0×10^{-3}	7.00	7.00×10^8	-0.28	24.4	-57.2	8.85	15.1
4-CH ₃	8.01×10^{-3}	1.80	2.78×10^9	-0.14	-	-	-	-
4-F	5.55×10^{-3}	0.80	6.30×10^9	0.06	17.8	-9.44	-	-
4-H	3.78×10^{-3}	1.20	2.00×10^9	0.00	27.0	-57.0	84.5	218
4-Cl	2.44×10^{-3}	0.60	8.33×10^9	0.24	19.3	-7.83	11.4	23.4

methylbenzyl-*gem*-dichlorides to form diffusionally-equilibrated carbocation intermediates which can be trapped by chloride ion and by solvent. The capture of α -chloro- α -methylbenzyl carbocations by added chloride ion leads to a reduction in their steady-state concentration and hence in k_{obsd} for solvolysis of the starting α -methylbenzyl-*gem*-dichlorides. The good fit to eq. (1), derived for the mechanism shown in Scheme 1, of the kinetic data for solvolysis of α -methylbenzyl-*gem*-dichlorides in the presence of increasing concentration of chloride ion shows that the reactions proceed through liberated carbocation intermediates. For example, from the plot of $k_{\text{solv}}/k_{\text{obsd}}$ versus $[\text{Cl}^-]$ the value of k_{Cl}/k_s was obtained for α -methylbenzyl-*gem*-dichloride. Therefore, absolute rate constants k_s (s^{-1}) for capture of α -chloro- α -methylbenzyl carbocations by water were obtained from the rate constant ratios k_{Cl}/k_s (M^{-1}) for partitioning of the cations and using a value of $k_{\text{Cl}} = 5 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the reaction of cation with Cl^- .

There is a 10-fold increase in k_{solv} for α -methylbenzyl-*gem*-dichloride as the ring substituent Y is changed from 4-Cl to 4-MeO (Table 1), which is consistent with a large development of positive charge at the benzylic carbon in the rate-determining transition state for solvolysis which was reflected from the good Hammett correlation with a $\rho_{\text{solv}} = -1.82$ which shows that the thermodynamic stability of cations is sensitive to the polar effects of the substituents to a larger extent. A similar good Hammett correlation was also observed for k_s with a $\sigma_s = 1.95$.

The negative values of entropy indicate reorganization of the solvent shell in the transition state as a result of hydration of ions. In fact during the solvolysis as the leaving group departs it acquires a solvent shell which is increasingly bonded to it⁵. Hence freezing of solvent molecules takes place as the solvolysis proceeds, hence negative entropies of activation for the solvolysis process.

The entropy values for addition of water to the cations are not negative as expected in *gem*-diazides but are moderately positive. This clearly reflects on the reactivity of α -methyl- α -chlorobenzyl carbocations are more reactive than α -azidobenzyl carbocations⁵ and less reactive than α -chlorobenzyl carbocations⁶ towards water and there is no time for the former to be solvated except showing high reactivity and giving rise the ions. This finally increases the total number of species that is responsible for more disorder

of the total system hence positive entropies. However, it is note worthy that the entropy values are less positive than those for α -chlorobenzyl carbocations.

The possibility of the formation of an elimination product i.e. an alkene from the intermediate cation is not ruled out as shown below⁷. I left it for future studies.

Experimental

All experimental details were similar to those reported earlier from our laboratory⁶.

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